

Braconid wasps (Hymenoptera, Braconidae) of the subfamily Microgastrinae in the fauna of Ukraine. 2. The tribe Apantelini

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Kotenko, A. G. Braconid wasps (Hymenoptera, Braconidae) of the subfamily Microgastrinae in the fauna of Ukraine. 2. The tribe Apantelini. — Based on material deposited in the I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology and Institute for Evolutionary Ecology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, as well as of the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (St. Petersburg) and the Zoological Museum of the Moscow State University (Moscow), taking into account the given literature, an annotated list of the Ukrainian braconid wasps of the tribe Apantelini was compiled. It includes 85 species from 4 genera. Of them, nine species of four genera (*Apanteles atreus*, *Dolichogenidea cheles*, *D. impura*, *D. jaroshevskiy*, *D. lineipes*, *Illidops electilis*, *Pholetesor exiguus*, *P. laetus*, *P. maritimus*) are recorded for the first time from Ukraine.

Key words: Braconidae, Microgastrinae, Apantelini, *Apanteles*, *Dolichogenidea*, *Illidops*, *Napamus*, *Pholetesor*, Ukraine.

Котенко, А. Г. Браконіди (Hymenoptera, Braconidae) підродини Microgastrinae у фауні України: 2. Триба Apantelini. — За матеріалами колекції Інституту зоології ім. І. І. Шмальгаузена та Інституту еволюційної екології НАНУ (Київ), а також Зоологічного інституту РАН (Санкт-Петербург) і Зоологічного музею МДУ (Москва), з урахуванням даних літератури, приводиться анований список браконідів триби Apantelini фауни України, що включає 85 видів з 4 родів. Дев'ять видів з чотирьох родів (*Apanteles atreus*, *Dolichogenidea cheles*, *D. impura*, *D. jaroshevskiy*, *D. lineipes*, *Illidops electilis*, *Pholetesor exiguus*, *P. laetus*, *P. maritimus*.) вперше зазначено для фауни України.

Ключові слова: Braconidae, Microgastrinae, Apantelini, *Apanteles*, *Dolichogenidea*, *Illidops*, *Napamus*, *Pholetesor*, Україна.

Introduction

The author of this article follows the system Microgastrinae, proposed by Mason (1981). The tribe Apantelini is one of the largest and most famous groups of the braconid wasps. It includes up to 3,000 or more species (Mason, 1981; Whitfield, 1997; Achterberg, 2002).

In the subfamily Microgastrinae, the tribe Apantelini includes the largest number of genera, more than 20 (according to Mason (1981) — sixteen), four of which have been recorded for the fauna of Ukraine (*Apanteles* Förster, 1862, *Dolichogenidea* Viereck, 1911, *Illidops* Mason, 1981, *Pholetesor* Mason, 1981). In total, 85 species of the tribe have been recorded from Ukraine.

The largest number of species is represented by the genera *Dolichogenidea* (46) and *Apanteles* (17). The genera *Pholetesor* and *Illidops* are represented by 12 and 10 species, respectively. Representatives of 32 families

of the order Lepidoptera are known to be the hosts of the microgastrine tribe Apantelini in the fauna of Ukraine. For *Dolichogenidea*, host species from 24 families of butterflies are indicated, for *Apanteles*, *Pholetesor* and *Illidops*, 18, 6, and 4 families, respectively. The largest number of species of the tribe Apantelini of the fauna of Ukraine is indicated as parasites by representatives of the families Tortricidae (31), Gracillariidae (22), and Coleophoridae (10).

Material and methods

This work is based on many years of research by the author in Ukraine and neighboring countries. The material was collected entomological net sweeping, breeding from the caterpillars Lepidoptera and cocoons Microgastrinae collected in the nature. Adult insects were also caught

using Merike traps. Collected Apantelini braconids (more than 4000 specimens) are deposited in the collection of the Institute of Zoology and Institute for Evolutionary Ecology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (Kyiv). Material on Apantelini from the collection of the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (St. Petersburg) and the Zoological Museum of Moscow State University (Moscow) were studied. The work also takes into account the data (on the distribution and host-parasitic connections) of a number of publications (Ivanov, 1898; Telenga, 1955; Tobias, 1971, 1976; Tobias, Kotenko, 1986; Kotenko, 1997, 1999, 2002, 2012, 2013, 2019 etc.), as well as the electronic databases FaunaEuropaea (<https://fauna-eu.org>) and Taxapad Ichneumonoidea. The classification and nomenclature of Lepidoptera (hosts of Apantelini) are given in accordance with the Catalog of Lepidoptera of Russia (2008).

Results

As a result, it has been established that in Ukraine there are 85 species of 4 genera belonging to the Apantelini tribe. Of them, 9 species of 4 genera are recorded for the first time in the fauna of Ukraine: *Apanteles atreus*, *Dolichogenidea cheles*, *D. impura*, *D. jaroshevskiyi*, *D. lineipes*, *Illidops electilis*, *Pholetesor exiguus*, *P. laetus*, *P. maritimus* (marked with asterisk: *). The largest number of tribe species was found in the South (66) and Central (49) regions of Ukraine, the smallest — in the North (15) and East (25). Species from the tribe Apantelini in Ukraine are found both in natural plant associations and in artificial plantations, including in agrocenoses. Some species (*Apanteles carpatus*, *A. galleriae*) can be found even in residential buildings or technical premises.

Among the apanteline there are many rare species, noted by single specimens. As a rule, their biology is not studied or is studied very poorly. There are many among the apanteline and common, often numerous species (*A. metacarpalis*, *A. obscures*, *A. sodalis*, *A. xanthostigma*, *D. albipennis*, *D. candidata*, *D. dilecta*, *D. emarginata*, *D. evonymellae*, *D. laevigata*, *D. sicaria*, *D. ultor*, *P. bicolor*, *P. circumscriptus*, *P. nanus*, *Ph.viminetorum*). The biology of many of them, especially the entomophages of known pests (*Archips rosanus* Linnaeus, *Etiella zinckenella* Treitschke, *Malacosoma neustrium* Linnaeus, *Phyllonorycter corylifoliella* Hübner, *Tortrix viridana* Linnaeus, *Yponomeuta evonymella* Linnaeus, etc.), has been well studied.

Tribe Apantelini

Genus *Apanteles* Förster, 1862

Type species: *Microgaster obscurus* Nees, 1834. Widely distributed cosmopolitan genus with c. 1200

species in the World, about 300 species in the Palearctic, and 17 species in Ukraine, of which one was recorded for the first time for Ukraine by the author. Species of this genus parasitize in Lepidoptera caterpillars of 18 families (most often Tortricidae).

Apanteles atreus Nixon, 1973*

Apanteles atreus Nixon, 1973: 199; Papp, 1984a: 269, 1984b: 162, 1988: 149, 2007: 105; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 416; Achterberg, 2002: 27.

Material. Ukraine: Odesa Region, Vilkovo, 06.1995, 1♀ (A. Kilimnik) (SIZK).

Distribution. Ukraine: South (Odesa Region). — Europe: Western Europe (Germany, Great Britain), Northern Europe (Denmark, Finland), Southern Europe (Greece, Italy), Eastern Europe (Czech Republic, Bulgaria, Hungary, Russia); Turkey, Iran.

Hosts. *Mompha propinquella* Stainton, *M. sturnipennella* Treitschke, *Psacaphora locupletella* Denis & Schiffermüller (Momphidae).

Apanteles brunnistigma Abdinbekova, 1969

Apanteles brunnistigma Abdinbekova, 1969: 74, 1975: 270; Tobias, 1976: 197; Papp, 1981b: 152, 1988: 149; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 455; Zerova, Kotenko *et al.*, 1989: 152; Zerova *et al.*, 1992: 21, 91, 178; Kotenko, 1997: 682, 1999: 544, 2013: 139.

Apanteles sotades Nixon, 1976: 703.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, Center, South. — Europe: Western Europe (France, Great Britain, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Italy), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Russia); Canary Islands; Asian Russia (Tomsk Region, Zabaikalskiy Territory, Primorsky Territory); Azerbaijan, Iran, Korea, Turkey; North America (Canada).

Hosts. Parasites of lepidopterans from the families Crambidae, Depressariidae, Epermeniidae, Oecophoridae, Tortricidae, including *Pyrausta aurata* Scopoli (Crambidae), *Agonopterix umbellana* Fabricius, *Depressaria ultimella* Stainton (Depressariidae), *Epermenia chaerophyllella* Goeze (Epermeniidae), *Aphelia viburnana* Denis & Schiffermüller, *Archips rosana* Linnaeus, *Gynnidomorpha vectisana* Hum. & West., *Rhopobota naevana* Hübner (Tortricidae).

Apanteles carpatus (Say, 1836)

Microgaster carpatus Say, 1836.

Apanteles carpatus: Nixon, 1965: 75; Tobias, 1976: 204; Nixon, 1976: 705; Papp, 1981b: 152; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 455; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 230; Kotenko, 1999: 544, 2013: 139.

Protapanteles hawaiiensis Ashmead, 1901.

Urogaster fuscicornis Cameron, 1910.

Apanteles piceiventris Muesebeck, 1921.

Apanteles igae Watanabe, 1932.

Apanteles sarcitorius Telenga, 1955: 55.

Apanteles ultericus Telenga, 1955: 57.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, North, Center, East, South, Crimea. — Cosmopolitan species.

Hosts. *Niditinea fuscella* Linnaeus, *Tinea columbariella* Wocke, *T. pelliionella* Linnaeus, *Tineola bisseliella* Hummel, *Trichophaga tapetzella* Linnaeus (Tineidae).

Apanteles corvinus Reinhard, 1880

Apanteles corvinus: Wilkinson, 1945: 146; Telenga, 1955: 85; Abdinbekova, 1975: 259; Tobias, 1976: 192; Papp, 1984a: 272, 1984b: 162; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 418; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 209; Zerova, Melika *et al.*, 1989: 41; Zerova *et al.*, 1992: 21, 91, 179; Kotenko, 1997: 682, 2013: 139.

Apanteles lucidus Szépligeti, 1896.

Apanteles rasteratus Fahringer, 1936.

Apanteles aptus Papp, 1977.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Estonia, Finland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden), Southern Europe (Greece), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia); Azerbaijan, Georgia, Japan, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan; Canada.

Hosts. Parasites of lepidopterans from the families Bucculatricidae, Coleophoridae, Lyonetiidae, Tortricidae, Yponomeutidae, including *Haploptilia coracipennella* Hübner, *H. serratella* Linnaeus (Coleophoridae), *Lyonetia clerkella* Linnaeus (Lyonetiidae), *Hedya dimidioalba* Retzius (Tortricidae), *Argyresthia semifusca* Haworth, *Paraswammerdamia lutarea* Haworth (Yponomeutidae).

Apanteles evanidus Papp, 1975

Apanteles evanidus Papp, 1975: 245; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 451; Papp, 1981b: 153, Papp, 1988: 149; Kotenko, 2013: 139.

Apanteles calpurnia Nixon, 1976.

Distribution. Ukraine: South. — Europe: Northern Europe (Finland, Sweden), Southern Europe (European Turkey), Eastern Europe (Hungary, Moldova, Russia).

Hosts. *Scythropia crataegella* Linnaeus, *Paraswammerdamia ornichella* Friese (Yponomeutidae).

Apanteles firmus Telenga, 1949

Telenga, 1949: 384; Telenga, 1955: 68; Tobias, 1971: 246; Abdinbekova, 1975: 259; Tobias, 1976: 192; Papp, 1984a: 267; Papp, 1984b: 162; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 408; Papp, 1988: 149.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, South. — Europe: Western Europe (France), Southern Europe (Serbia), Eastern Europe (Hungary, Romania, Russia); Asian Russia (Zabaikalskiy Territory, Primorsky Territory); Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Mongolia, Tajikistan.

Hosts. *Acleris quercinana* Zeller (Tortricidae).

Apanteles galleriae Wilkinson, 1932

Apanteles galleriae: Fahringer, 1935: 177; Telenga, 1955: 60; Nixon, 1965: 75, 1976: 707; Papp, 1981b: 153, 1988: 149; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 455; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 229; Kotenko, 2007: 169; Shaw, 2012: 175.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, Center, East, South. — Europe: Western Europe (France, Great Britain), Southern

Europe (Greece, Italy, Spain), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania, Russia); Asian Russia (Ural, Altay Territory, Amur Region and Primorskiy Territory); Armenia, China (SW, CC, SE), Iran, Japan, Pakistan, Turkey; Africa; Canada, USA; South America; India; New Zealand.

Hosts. *Achroia grisella* Fabricius, *Galleria mellonella* Linnaeus (Pyralidae, Galleriinae).

Apanteles horaeus Kotenko, 1986

Apanteles horaeus Kotenko in: Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 455; Papp, 1988: 149; Kotenko, 2013: 139.

Distribution. Ukraine: South (Black Sea Biosphere Reserve). — Europe: Eastern Europe (Russia).

Hosts. Unknown.

Apanteles kubensis Abdinbekova, 1969

Apanteles kubensis Abdinbekova, 1969: 73, 1975: 266; Tobias, 1976: 204; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 452; Papp, 1988: 149; Kotenko, 1999: 545, 2013: 139.

Distribution. Ukraine: South (Black Sea Biosphere Reserve). — Europe: Eastern Europe (Hungary, Moldova, Russia); Azerbaijan, Korea, Mongolia, Turkey.

Hosts. *Adoxophyes orana* Fischer von Röslerstamm (Tortricidae).

Apanteles lenea Nixon, 1976

Apanteles lenea Nixon, 1976: 701; Papp, 1981b: 152, 1988: 149, 1999: 558; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 451; Zerova *et al.*, 1996: 17; Kotenko, 1997: 683; Shaw, 2012: 175.

Distribution. Ukraine: West (Carpathian Reserve), Center. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, France, Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland), Northern Europe (Finland, Sweden), Southern Europe (Italy, Serbia, Spain), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Slovakia, Romania, Russia); Asian Russia (Zabaikalskiy Territory, Primorsky Territory, Sakhalin Is.); Korea, Turkey.

Hosts. Lepidopterans from the families Cosmopterigidae, Pyralidae, Tortricidae, including *Panccalia schwarzzella* Fabricius (Cosmopterigidae), *Oncocera semirubella* Scopoli (Pyralidae), *Argyropluce arbutella* Linnaeus (Tortricidae).

Apanteles metacarpalis (Thomson, 1895)

Microgaster metacarpalis Thomson, 1895.

Apanteles metacarpalis: Telenga, 1955: 80; Nixon, 1965: 150, 1973: 199; Tobias, 1971: 251, 1976: 189; Abdinbekova, 1975: 257; Papp, 1984a: 271, 1984b: 162, 1988: 149, 1999: 558, 2014: 152; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 416; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 207; Kotenko, 1999: 545, 2013: 139.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (France, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Sweden), Southern Europe (Greece, Italy, Serbia, Spain), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Moldova, Romania, Slovakia, Russia); Asian Russia (Zabaikalskiy Territory,

Primorsky Territory); Azerbaijan, China, Iran, Kazakhstan, Korea, Mongolia, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan; Tunisia.

Hosts. Lepidopterans of the families Coleophoridae, Gelechiidae, Gracillariidae, including *Scrobipalpa samadensis* Pfaffenzeller (Gelechiidae), *Caloptilia seemifascia* Haworth (Gracillariidae).

Apanteles nephus Papp, 1974

Apanteles nephus Papp, 1974: 328, 1988: 151; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 417.

Distribution. Ukraine: South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, France, Germany), Eastern Europe (Hungary, Russia); Asian Russia (Primorsky Territory); China.

Hosts. Unknown.

Apanteles obscurus (Nees, 1834)

Microgaster obscurus Nees, 1834.

Apanteles obscurus: Ivanov, 1898: 62; Fahringer, 1935: 195; Wilkinson, 1945: 184; Telenga, 1955: 58; Abdinbekova, 1975: 268; Nixon, 1976: 700; Tobias, 1976: 197; Papp, 1981b: 152, 1999: 558, 2012: 180, 2014: 152; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 451; Lăcătușu & Filipescu 1989: 221; Kotenko, 1997: 683, 1999: 545, 2013: 139.

Microgaster arenarius Haliday, 1834.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, North, Center, East, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Denmark, Finland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden), Southern Europe (Albania, Croatia, Cyprus, Greece (incl. Crete), Italy, Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, Slovenia, Spain), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Primorskiy Territory, Sakhalin Is.); Armenia, Azerbaijan, Middle Asia, Georgia, Israel, Iran, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Turkey; Tunisia.

Hosts. *Algedonia terrealis* Treitschke, *Ebulea crocealis* Hübner, *Udea ferrugalis* Hübner (Crambidae), *Epermenia chaerophylla* Goeze (Epermeniidae), *Chlorissa viridata* Linnaeus (Geometridae), *Acleris forsskaleana* Linnaeus, *Clepsis pallidana* Fabricius, *Pammene germmanna* Hübner (Tortricidae).

Apanteles peisonis Fischer, 1965

Apanteles peisonis: Papp, 1988: 150; Kotenko, 1999: 545; Kotenko, 2013: 139.

Apanteles subfirmus Abdinbekova, 1969, 1975: 258; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 415

Distribution. Ukraine: South (Dunaisky Biosphere Reserve and Black Sea Biosphere Reserve). — Europe: Western Europe (Austria), Eastern Europe (Hungary, Romania, Russia); Azerbaijan.

Hosts. *Carpochena salicorniae* Heinemann & Wocke (Coleophoridae).

Apanteles prinoptus Papp, 1984

Apanteles prinoptus Papp, 1984: 266, 274; 1988: 150; Kotenko, 1999: 545.

Apanteles metaclypealis Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 416.

Distribution. Ukraine: South (Melitopol, Dunaisky Biosphere Reserve). — Europe: Western Europe (Germany), Eastern Europe (Hungary, Russia).

Hosts. Unknown.

Apanteles sodalis (Haliday, 1834)

Microgaster sodalis Haliday, 1834

Apanteles sodalis: Ivanov, 1898: 63, 93; Tobias, 1971: 243; Nixon, 1976: 707; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 451; Papp, 1988: 150; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 227; Zerova, Kotenko *et al.*, 1989: 152; Zerova *et al.*, 1992: 21, 31, 40; Kotenko, 2013: 139.

Microgaster carbonarius Ratzeburg, 1848.

Microgaster ater Ratzeburg, 1852.

Apanteles ater: Telenga, 1955: 61.

Microgaster lugens Ratzeburg, 1852.

Apanteles lindbergi Hedqvist, 1965.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, North, Center, East, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (France, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Latvia, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Serbia, Spain), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Khabarovsk, Primorskiy Territory, Sakhalin Is.); Armenia, Azerbaijan, Middle Asia, China, Georgia, Iran, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Turkey; Canada (introduced).

Hosts. Lepidopterans from the families Depressariidae, Geometridae, Tortricidae, including *Depressaria depressana* Fabricius (Depressariidae), *Operophtera brumata* Linnaeus (Geometridae), *Acleris rhombana* Denis & Schiffermüller, *Adoxophyes orana* Fischer von Röslerstamm, *Archips crataeganus* Hübner, *A. podanus* Scopoli, *A. rosanus* Linnaeus, *A. xylosteanus* Linnaeus, *Epinotia nigricana* Herrich-Schäffer, *Grapholita funebrana* Treitschke, *G. janthinana* Dup., *Hedya dimidioalba* Retzius, *Laspeyresia pomonella* Linnaeus, *Pandemis heparana* Denis & Schiffermüller, *Spilonota ocellana* Fabricius (Tortricidae).

Apanteles xanthostigma (Haliday, 1834)

Microgaster xanthostigma Haliday, 1834.

Apanteles xanthostigma: Ivanov, 1898: 60; Telenga, 1955: 60; Tobias, 1971: 257; Abdinbekova, 1973: 75; Nixon, 1976: 701; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 452; Papp, 1988: 150; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 227; Zerova, Kotenko *et al.*, 1989: 152; Zerova *et al.*, 1992: 21, 31, 40, 250; Kotenko, 1997: 683; Kotenko, 2013: 139.

Microgaster ochrostigma Wesmael, 1837.

Apanteles xanthocarpus Szépliget, 1901.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, North, Center, East, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Lichtenstein, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Latvia, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Serbia, Spain (incl. Canary

Is.)), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia; Armenia, Azerbaijan, China, Georgia, Iran, Japan, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Mongolia, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan; North Africa; Canada (introduced).

Hosts. Lepidopterans from the families Choreutidae, Gelechiidae, Geometridae, Gracillariidae, Pyralidae, Tortricidae, Yponomeutidae, including *Choreutis diana* Hübner, *Ch. pariana* Clerck (Choreutidae), *Agriopsis bajaria* Denis & Schiffermüller, *Operophtera brumata* Linnaeus (Geometridae), *Callisto denticulella* Thunberg, *Caloptilia betulicola* Hering, *C. elongella* Linnaeus, *C. stigmatella* Fabricius, *Parornix devoniella* Stainton, *P. scoticella* Stt, *Povolnya leucapennella* Stephens (Gracillariidae), *Trachycera suavella* Zin. (Pyralidae), *Acleris hastiana* Linnaeus, *Adoxophyes orana* Fischer von Röslerstamm, *Ancylis achatana* Denis & Schiffermüller, *Archips crateganus* Hübner, *A. rosanus* Linnaeus, *A. xylosteanus* Linnaeus, *Hedya dimidioalba* Retzius, *H. pruniana* Hübner, *Gypsonoma minutana* Hübner, *Pandemis cerasana* Hübner, *Rhopobota naevana* Hübner, *Spilonota ocellana* Denis & Schiffermüller, *Tortrix viridana* Linnaeus (Tortricidae), *Paraswammerdamia albicapitella* Scharf., *P. lutarea* Haworth, *Swammerdamia caesiella* Hübner, *S. pyrella* Villers (Yponomeutidae).

Genus *Dolichogenidea* Viereck, 1911

Type species: *Dolichogenidea banksi* Viereck, 1911.

A widely distributed cosmopolitan genus. It includes about 1000 species (in the Palaearctic Region — about 150), with 46 species in Ukraine, of which four (*Dolichogenidea cheles*, *D. impura*, *D. jaroshevskiyi*, *D. lineipes*) were recorded for the first time from Ukraine by the author. Species of this genus parasitize in Lepidoptera caterpillars of 24 families (most often Tortricidae, Gracillariidae, Gelechiidae, Plutellidae).

Dolichogenidea albipennis (Nees, 1834)

Microgaster albipennis Nees, 1834.

Apanteles albipennis: Ivanov, 1898: 64; Telenga, 1955: 82; Tobias, 1971: 242; Tobias, 1976: 196; Papp, 1981b: 146, Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 441; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 244; Zerova, Melika *et al.*, 1989: 40.

Dolichogenidea albipennis: Papp, 1999: 560.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (France, Germany, Great Britain, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Denmark, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Albania, France (Corsica), Italy), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia); Asian Russia (Primorsky Territory); Afghanistan, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Turkmenistan, Turkey.

Hosts. Lepidopterans from the families Gelechiidae, Sesiidae and Tortricidae, including *Aristotelia brizella* Treitschke, *Caryocolum tricolorella* Haworth (Gelechiidae), *Synanthedon tipuliformis* Clerk (Sesiidae), *Aethes francillana* Fabricius, *Archips rosanus* Linnaeus,

A. xylosteanus Linnaeus, *Cnephasia sedana* Constant, *Tortrix viridana* Linnaeus (Tortricidae).

Dolichogenidea anarsiae (Faure & Alabouvette, 1924)

Apanteles anarsiae Faure & Alabouvette, 1924; Wilkinson, 1945: 208; Telenga, 1955: 63; Tobias, 1976: 206; Nixon, 1976: 697; Papp, 1983: 126; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 458, 2007: 182; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 226; Zerova *et al.*, 1992: 20, 40, 91, 178.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, South. — Europe: Western Europe (France, Great Britain, Switzerland), Southern Europe (Greece, Italy), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Moldova, Romania, Russia); Asian Russia (Primorsky Territory); Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Turkey; China, U.S.A. (introduced).

Hosts. *Ananarsia eleagnella* Kuznetzov, *A. lineatella* Zeller, *Helcystogramma triannulella* Herrich-Schäffer (Gelechiidae), *Grapholitha funebrana* Treitschke, *G. molesta* Busck (Tortricidae).

Dolichogenidea annularis (Haliday, 1834)

Microgaster annularis Haliday, 1834

Apanteles annularis Telenga, 1955: 100; Tobias, 1971: 242; Nixon, 1972: 711; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 437.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, South. — Europe: Western Europe (France, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Switzerland), Northern Europe (Sweden), Southern Europe (Italy), Eastern Europe (Hungary, Poland, Russia); Asian Russia (Zabaikalskiy Territory, Amur Region); Georgia.

Hosts. Lepidopterans from the families Gracillariidae and Tortricidae, including *Caloptilia fribergensis* Fritzsche, *C. rufipennella* Hübner (Gracillariidae), *Cnephasia asseclana* Denis & Schiffermüller, *C. chrysantheana* Duponchel, *C. incertana* Treitschke, *C. longana* Haworth, *Cydia pomonella* Linnaeus (Tortricidae).

Dolichogenidea appellator (Telenga, 1949)

Apanteles appellator Telenga, 1949: 385, 1955: 91; Nixon, 1972: 710; Tobias, 1976: 195; Papp, 1981b: 145, Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 428; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 240.

Dolichogenidea appellator: Shaw, 2012: 176; Kotenko, 2013: 140; Papp, 2014: 153.

Apanteles salverdensis Hedqvist, 1965.

Apanteles litae Nixon, 1972.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, Center, East, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland), Southern Europe (Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Serbia, Spain), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Hungary, Moldova, Romania, Russia); Asian Russia (Primorsky Territory); Afghanistan, Armenia, Azerbaijan, China (NE), Iran, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Oman, Saudi Arabia, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, United Arab Emirates, Uzbekistan, Yemen; North Africa: Cape Verde Is.

Hosts. Lepidopterans from the families Crambidae, Gelechiidae, Plutellidae, Pyralidae, including *Pyrausta purpuralis* Linnaeus, *P. sanguinalis* Linnaeus (Crambidae), *Phthorimaea operculella* Zeller, *Scrobipalpa ocellatella*

Boyd, *S. salinella* Zeller (Gelechiidae), *Plutella xylostella* Linnaeus (Plutellidae), *Etiella zinckenella* Treitschke (Pyralidae).

Dolichogenidea azovica (Kotenko, 1986)

Apanteles azovica Kotenko in: Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 442.

Distribution. Ukraine: South, Crimea. — Europe: Eastern Europe (Poland, Russia).

Hosts. Unknown.

Dolichogenidea benkevitchi (Kotenko, 1986)

Apanteles benkevitchi Kotenko in: Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 443.

Distribution. Ukraine: Crimea. — Europe: Eastern Europe (Russia).

Hosts. Unknown.

Dolichogenidea borysthenica (Kotenko, 1986)

Apanteles borysthenica Kotenko in: Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 441; Kotenko, 2013: 140.

Distribution. Ukraine: South (Black Sea Biosphere Reserve). — Europe: Eastern Europe (Russia).

Hosts. Unknown.

Dolichogenidea breviventris (Ratzeburg, 1848)

Microgaster breviventris Ratzeburg, 1848.

Apanteles breviventris: Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 433; Papp, 1988: 147; Zerova, Melika *et al.*, 1989: 40; Lăcătușu, Filipescu, 1989: 253.

Apanteles mesoxanthus Ruschka, 1917.

Apanteles nilae Telenga, 1961.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, East, South. — Europe: Western Europe (Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Italy), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Egypt, Korea, Turkey; Canada.

Hosts. Lepidoptera from the genus *Coleophora* (Coleophoridae).

Dolichogenidea candidata (Haliday, 1834)

Microgaster candidata Haliday, 1834.

Apanteles candidatus: Tobias, 1976: 199; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 445; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 251; Zerova, Melika *et al.*, 1989: 42, 153; Zerova *et al.*, 1992: 21, 57, 92, 181

Dolichogenidea candidata: Achterberg, 2002: 27.

Microgaster coniferarum Haliday, 1834.

Microgaster longicaudus Wesm., 1837; Telenga, 1955: 89; Nixon, 1972: 723.

Microgaster terebrator Ratzeburg, 1852.

Dolichogenidea candidata: Shaw, 2012: 177; Kotenko, 2013: 140.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, North, Center, East, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Belgium, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, the Netherlands, Switzerland), Northern Europe (Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Greece, Italy, Macedonia, Serbia, Spain), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia,

Slovakia); Asian Russia (Khabarovsk Territory, Primorsky Territory, Sakhalin Is.), Afghanistan, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan; Cape Verde Is.

Hosts. Lepidoptera from the families Agonoxenidae, Bucculatricidae, Choreutidae, Depressariidae, Gelechiidae, Gracillariidae, Oecophoridae, Plutellidae, Pyralidae, Tortricidae, Yponomeutidae, including *Blastodacna atra* Haworth (Agonoxenidae) *Bucculatrix cristatella* Linnaeus (Bucculatricidae), *Choreutis pariana* Clerck (Choreutidae), *Agonopterix ocellana* Fabricius (Depressariidae), *Ananarsia eleagnella* Kuznetsov, *A. lineatella* Zeller (Gelechiidae), *Carcina quercana* Fabricius (Oecophoridae), *Plutella xylostella* Linnaeus (Plutellidae), *Etiella zinckenella* Treitschke (Pyralidae), *Acleris literana* Linnaeus, *A. quercinana* Zeller, *Archips oporanus* Linnaeus, *A. rosanus* Linnaeus, *Epinotia nigricana* Herrich-Schäffer, *Hedya pruniana* Hübner, *Pandemis chondrillana* Herrich-Schäffer, *Spilonota ocellana* Denis & Schiffermüller, *Tortrix viridana* Linnaeus (Tortricidae), *Paraswammerdamia lutarea* Haworth (Yponomeutidae).

Dolichogenidea cerialis (Nixon, 1976)

Apanteles cerialis Nixon, 1976: 698; Papp, 1983: 126; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 459; Zerova, Melika *et al.*, 1989: 41.

Apanteles areolaris Balevski & Tobias, 1980.

Distribution. Ukraine: South. — Europe: Western Europe (Great Britain), Southern Europe (Italy, Spain), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Russia); Israel, Kazakhstan.

Hosts. *Ascotis selenaria* Denis & Schiffermüller (Geometridae).

Dolichogenidea cheles (Nixon, 1972)*

Apanteles cheles Nixon, 1972: 720; Papp, 1981b: 146; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 437.

Material. Odesa Region: Vilkovo, 18.06.1995, 2♀ (A. Kotenko) (SIZK).

Distribution. Ukraine: West, North. — Europe: Western Europe (Great Britain, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Sweden), Southern Europe (European Turkey), Eastern Europe (Hungary, Poland, Romania, Russia).

Hosts. *Caloptilia fribergensis* Fritzsche, *C. rufipennella* Hübner (Gracillariidae) and *Acleris (Croesia) holmiana* Linnaeus (Tortricidae).

Dolichogenidea coleophorae (Wilkinson, 1938)

Apanteles coleophorae Wilkinson, 1938; Telenga, 1955: Tobias, 1976: 206; 189; Nixon, 1976: 697; Papp, 1976b: 102, 114; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 457; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 225.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, South. — Europe: Western Europe (Great Britain, Switzerland), Northern Europe (Finland), Eastern Europe (Hungary, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Khabarovsk

Territory); Azerbaijan, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan; Tunisia; Canada.

Hosts. *Haploptilia serratella* Linnaeus, *Zagulajevia tadzhiikiella* Danilevsky (Coleophoridae).

Dolichogenidea cytherea (Nixon, 1972)

Apanteles cytherea Nixon, 1972; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 357.

Distribution. Ukraine: South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Germany, Great Britain, France, Switzerland), Southern Europe (Greece, Serbia), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Russia, Slovakia); Iran, Mongolia.

Hosts. *Eurrhyncha hortulata* Linnaeus (Crambidae), *Ypsolopha alpella* Denis & Schiffermüller (Ypsolophidae).

Dolichogenidea decora (Haliday, 1834)

Microgaster decorus Haliday, 1834.

Apanteles decorus: Tobias, 1976: 196; Papp, 1981b: 146; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 443; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 244.

Apanteles lineatus Reinhard, 1880; Telenga, 1955: 75.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, North, Center, East, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Estonia, Finland, Latvia, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Greece, Italy, Spain), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Irkutsk Region, Khabarovsk Territory); China, Georgia, Iran, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan.

Hosts. Parasite of lepidopterans from the families Gracillariidae, Tortricidae, Yponomeutidae, including *Aethes dilucidana* Stephens, *Gypsonoma minutana* Hübner, *Rhyacionia duplana* Hübner, *Zeiraphera rufimitrana* Herrich-Schäffer (Tortricidae), *Argyresthia goedartella* Linnaeus (Yponomeutidae).

Dolichogenidea dilecta (Haliday, 1834)

Microgaster dilectus Haliday, 1834.

Apanteles dilectus: Ivanov, 1898: 59; Telenga, 1955: 75; Tobias, 1971: 246; Nixon, 1972: 719; Tobias, 1976: 195; Papp, 1981b: 146; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 435; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 242; Zerova, Melika *et al.*, 1989: 41; Zerova *et al.*, 1992: 21, 51, 91, 181; Kotenko, 1997: 683.

Dolichogenidea dilecta: Kotenko, 2013: 140.

Microgaster femoralis Bouché, 1834.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, North, Center, East, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, France, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Sweden), Southern Europe (Italy, Spain), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Khabarovsk Territory, Sakhalin Is.); Armenia, China, Japan, Korea, Turkey.

Hosts. Lepidopterans from the families Gracillariidae, Tortricidae, Yponomeutidae, including *Acrocercops brongniardella* Fabricius, *Caloptilia betulicola* Hering,

C. elongella Linnaeus, *C. roscipennella* Hübner, *Gracillaria syringella* Fabricius (Gracillariidae), *Aleimma loeflingiana* Linnaeus, *Archips crataeganus* Hübner, *Choristoneura murinana* Hübner, *Dichelia histrionana* Frölich, *Epinotia pygmaeana* Hübner, *Grapholita inopinata* Heinrich, *Hedya pruniana* Hübner, *Tortrix viridana* Linnaeus, *Zeiraphera rufimitrana* Herrich-Schäffer (Tortricidae), *Yponomeuta cagnagella* Hübner, *Y. padella* Linnaeus (Yponomeutidae).

Dolichogenidea drusilla (Nixon, 1972)

Apanteles drusillus Nixon, 1972: 715; Papp, 1981b: 146; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 439.

Dolichogenidea drusilla Papp, 1999: 560.

Distribution. Ukraine: South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Germany, Great Britain), Northern Europe (Sweden), Southern Europe (Italy), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Primorsky Territory); Georgia, Mongolia, Turkey.

Hosts. Unknown.

Dolichogenidea emarginata (Nees, 1834)

Microgaster emarginatus Nees, 1834

Apanteles emarginatus: Telenga, 1955: 81; Nixon, 1972: 710; Tobias, 1976: 195; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 437; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 254; Zerova *et al.*, 1992: 35, 40, 91, 181.

Microgaster scapularis Bouché, 1834.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, North, Center, East, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland), Northern Europe (Iceland, Latvia, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Italy, Spain), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Altay Territory, Khabarovsk Territory, Primorsky Territory); Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran, Israel, Kazakhstan, Turkey.

Hosts. Lepidopterans from the families Depressariidae, Gelechiidae, Gracillariidae, Oecophoridae, Tortricidae, Yponomeutidae, including *Agonopterix alstromeriana* Clerck, *A. arenella* Denis & Schiffermüller, *A. atomella* Denis & Schiffermüller, *A. carduella* Hübner, *A. propiguella* Treitschke, *Depressaria chaerophylli* Zeller, *D. radiella* Goeze, *D. rubricella* Denis & Schiffermüller (Depressariidae), *Caloptilia fribergensis* Fritzsche, *C. rufipennella* Hübner (Gracillariidae), *Acleris forsskaleana* Linnaeus, *Aethes dilucidana* Steph, *Aleimma loeflingiana* Linnaeus, *Archips xylosteanus* Linnaeus, *Choristoneura diversana* Hübner, *Cnephasia stephensiana* Doubleday, *Dichelia histrionana* Frölich, *Laspeyresia pomonella* Linnaeus (Tortricidae), *Yponomeuta evonymella* Linnaeus (Yponomeutidae).

Dolichogenidea erdoesi (Papp, 1973)

Apanteles erdoesi Papp, 1973: 292; Tobias, 1976: 246; Papp, 1988: 147; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 417.

Apanteles negativus Tobias, 1976.

Distribution. Ukraine: South. — Europe: Eastern Europe (Hungary, Russia); Azerbaijan.

Hosts. Unknown.

Dolichogenidea evonymellae (Bouché, 1834)

Microgaster evonymellae Bouché, 1834.

Apanteles evonymellae: Telenga, 1955: 96; Papp, 1981b: Tobias, 1971: 246; 147; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 433; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 240; Zerova, Kotenko *et al.*, 1989: 153.

Dolichogenidea evonymellae: Kotenko, 2013: 140.

Apanteles iarbas Nixon, 1972.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, South. — Europe: Western Europe (Germany, Great Britain, the Netherlands), Southern Europe (Italy, Portugal, former Yugoslavia), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Romania, Russia); Armenia, Azerbaijan.

Hosts. Parasites of *Synanthedon tipuliformis* Clerck (Sesiidae), *Grapholita funebrana* Treitschke, *Spilonota ocellana* Denis & Schiffmüller, *Tortrix viridana* Linnaeus (Tortricidae), *Yponomeuta evonymella* Linnaeus, *Y. padella* Linnaeus (Yponomeutidae).

Dolichogenidea gagates (Nees, 1834)

Microgaster gagates Nees, 1834.

Apanteles gagates: Wilkinson, 1945: 181; Telenga, 1955: 85; Nixon, 1972: 722; Tobias, 1976: 197; Papp, 1981b: 147, Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 445; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 248; Zerova, Melika *et al.*, 1989: 41; Zerova *et al.*, 1992: 21, 91, 181.

Dolichogenidea gagates: Shaw, 2012: 178.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, South. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland), Northern Europe (Estonia, Finland, Latvia, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Italy, Spain), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia); Georgia.

Hosts. *Abraxas grossulariata* Linnaeus (Geometridae), *Stenoptilia bipunctidactyla* Scopoli (Pterophoridae), *Pandemis heparana* Denis & Schiffmüller, *Spilonota ocellana* Denis & Schiffmüller (Tortricidae).

Dolichogenidea gracilariae (Wilkinson, 1940)

Apanteles gagates Wilkinson, 1940: 26; Tobias, 1971: 248; Nixon, 1972: 733; Tobias, 1976: 199; Papp, 1981b: 147, Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 445; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 249.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Estonia, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Serbia, Spain), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran, Kazakhstan, Turkey, Uzbekistan.

Hosts. Parasites of *Gracillaria cuculipennella* Hübner, *G. syringella* Fabricius (Gracillariidae), *Lyonetia clerkella* Linnaeus (Lyonetiidae), *Plutella xylostella* Linnaeus (Plutellidae).

Dolichogenidea grata (Kotenko, 1986)

Apanteles gratus Kotenko in: Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 425.

Dolichogenidea gratus: Papp, 1988: 147.

Distribution. Ukraine: Crimea. — Europe: Eastern Europe (Russia).

Hosts. Unknown.

Dolichogenidea holidayi (Marshall, 1872)

Apanteles holidayi Marshall, 1872; Telenga, 1955: 90; Tobias, 1971: 248; Nixon, 1972: 726; Papp, 1981b: 147; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 445; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 238.

Dolichogenidea holidayi: Papp, 1999: 560; Shaw, 2012: 178.

Distribution. Ukraine: North, Center. — Europe: Western Europe (Germany, Great Britain, Ireland), Northern Europe (Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Sweden), Southern Europe (Croatia, Greece, Italy, Macedonia), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania, Russia); Armenia, Iran.

Hosts. Lepidopterans from the families Coleophoridae, Gelechiidae, Gracillariidae, Tortricidae, including *Goniodoma limoniella* Stainton (Coleophoridae), *Ptocheuusa inopella* Zeller (Gelechiidae), *Glyphipterix simplicella* Stephens (Glyphipterigidae), *Parectopa ononidis* Zeller (Gracillariidae), *Gypsonoma sociana* Haworth (Tortricidae).

Dolichogenidea helleni (Nixon, 1972)

Apanteles helleni Nixon, 1972: 729; Papp, 1981b: 148; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 441.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center. — Europe: Western Europe (Germany), Northern Europe (Finland), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Russia).

Hosts. Unknown.

Dolichogenidea imperator (Wilkinson, 1939)

Apanteles imperator Wilkinson, 1939: 57; Tobias, 1971: 248; Nixon, 1972: 721; Abdinbekova, 1973: 75; Abdinbekova, 1975: 263; Tobias, 1976: 199; Papp, 1981b: 148; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 444; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 246; Kotenko, 1997: 683.

Dolichogenidea imperator: Papp, 1999: 560.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, Center, East. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Lithuania), Southern Europe (Italy), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Romania, Russia); Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan.

Hosts. Lepidopterans from the families Acrolepiidae, Depressariidae, Epermeniidae, Geometridae, Plutellidae, including *Acrolepia autumnitella* Curtis (Acrolepiidae), *Agonopterix assimilella* Treitschke, *A. heracleana* Linnaeus, *Depressaria rubricella* Denis & Schiffmüller (Depressariidae), *Epermenia (Calotripis) aequidentella* E. Hofmann, *E. (Calotripis) chaerophylla* Goeze (Epermeniidae), *Chesias legatella* Denis & Schiffmüller (Geometridae), *Pseudoplutella porrectella* Linnaeus (Plutellidae).

Dolichogenidea impura* (Nees, 1834)*Microgaster impurus* Nees, 1834.*Apanteles impurus* Telenga, 1955: 95; Abdinbekova, 1975: 264; Papp, 1981b: 148; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 425.**Material.** Kyiv, 06.2005, 3 ♀ (A. Kotenko) (SIZK).**Distribution.** Ukraine: Center, — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland), Northern Europe (Latvia, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Greece, Italy), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Russia); Asian Russia (Eastern Siberia, Sakhalin Is.); Azerbaijan, China, Mongolia.**Hosts.** Parasites of *Gracillaria syringella* Fabricius (Gracillariidae), *Cnaemidophorus rhododactyla* Denis & Schiffermüller (Pterophoridae), *Cydia pactolana* Zeller, *Lozotaenia forsterana* Fabricius (Tortricidae).***Dolichogenidea infima* (Haliday, 1834)***Microgaster infimus* Haliday, 1834.*Apanteles infimus*: Wilkinson, 1939: 53; Telenga, 1955: 93, 1971: 248; Nixon, 1972: 726; Abdinbekova, 1975: 263; Tobias, 1976: 197; Papp, 1981b: 148; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 445; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 239.*Dolichogenidea infima*: Papp, 1999: 560.**Distribution.** Ukraine: Center, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (France, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Italy, Macedonia, Serbia), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Zabaikalskiy Territory, Primorsky Territory); Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Turkey, Uzbekistan.**Hosts.** Parasites of *Acrolepia autumnitella* Curtis (Acrolepiidae), *Tuberculia albitarsella* Zeller (Coleophoridae), *Epermenia (Calotripis) chaerophylella* Gooze (Epermeniidae), *Epinotia pygmaeana* Hübner, *Tortrix viridana* Linnaeus (Tortricidae).***Dolichogenidea jaroshevskiyi* (Tobias, 1976)****Apanteles jaroshevskiyi* Tobias, 1976: 250; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 457.**Material.** Kyiv Region: no collection date, 3♂, 5♀ (A. Kotenko) (SIZK).**Distribution.** Ukraine: East (Kharkov Region). — Europe: Eastern Europe (Russia); Armenia.**Hosts.** Parasites of *Gypsonoma minutana* Hübner (Tortricidae).***Dolichogenidea lactea* (Nees, 1834)***Microgaster lacteus* Nees, 1834.*Apanteles tadzhicus* Telenga, 1949.*Apanteles lacteus*: Ivanov, 1898: 59; Telenga, 1955: 79; Nixon, 1965: 129; Nixon, 1976: 693; Tobias, 1976: 201; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 447; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 236.*Dolichogenidea lactea*: Shaw, 2012: 175; Papp, 2014: 153.**Distribution.** Ukraine: Center, East, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland), Southern Europe (Greece, Italy), Eastern Europe (Czech Republic, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Orenburg Region); Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran, Israel, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkey, Uzbekistan; Tunisia.**Hosts.** Parasites of *Dioryctria abietella* Denis & Schiffermüller, *Etiella zinckenella* Treitschke, *Homoeosoma nebulellum* Denis & Schiffermüller, *H. (Anhomoeosoma) nimbella* Dup., *Phycitodes maritime* Teng. (Pyralidae).***Dolichogenidea lacteicolor* (Viereck, 1911)***Apanteles lacteicolor* Viereck, 1911; Wilkinson, 1945: 203; Telenga, 1955: 61; Abdinbekova, 1973: 75; Abdinbekova, 1975: 269; Nixon, 1976: 696; Tobias, 1976: 205; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 457; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 223; Zerova, Kotenko *et al.*, 1989: 152*Dolichogenidea lacteicolor*: Papp, 2012: 184.*Apanteles conspersae* Fiske, 1911.**Distribution.** Ukraine: Center, East, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, France, Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Lithuania), Southern Europe (Italy, Spain), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Afghanistan, Armenia, Azerbaijan, China, Iran, Israel, Japan, Tajikistan, Turkey, Uzbekistan; North America (introd.).**Hosts.** Parasites of *Acronicta psi* Linnaeus, *Nycteola asiatica* Krulikovskiy (Noctuidae), *Cerura vinula* Linnaeus, *Dicranura ulmi* Denis & Schiffermüller (Notodontidae), *Grapholitha funebrana* Treitschke, *Hedya dimidioalba* Retzius (Tortricidae).***Dolichogenidea laevigata* (Ratzeburg, 1848)***Microgaster laevigatus* Ratzeburg, 1848.*Apanteles laevigatus*: Wilkinson, 1945: 167; Telenga, 1955: 69; Nixon, 1965: 181, 1972: 712; Tobias, 1971: 249; Abdinbekova, 1973: 75, 1975: 260; Tobias, 1976: 193; Papp, 1981b: 149; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 433; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 241; Zerova, Kotenko *et al.*, 1989: 152; Zerova *et al.*, 1992: 21, 92, 181.*Dolichogenidea laevigata*: Kotenko, 2013: 140.*Microgaster hoplites* Ratzeburg, 1848.**Distribution.** Ukraine: West, North, Center, East, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (France, Germany, Great Britain, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Latvia, Lithuania), Southern Europe (Italy, Serbia, Spain), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Altay Territory, Primorsky Territory); Armenia, Azerbaijan, China, Georgia, Israel, Kazakhstan, Korea, Turkey, Uzbekistan.**Hosts.** Parasites of *Choreutis pariana* Clerck (Choreutidae), *Anacamptis populella* Clerck, *Gelechia rhombella* Denis & Schiffermüller, *G. sesteriella* Herrich-Schäffer, *G. turpella* Denis & Schiffermüller (Gelechiidae),

Acleris (Croesia) bergmanniana Linnaeus, *A. (Croesia) forsskaleana* Linnaeus, *Archips rosana* Linnaeus, *A. xylosteanus* Linnaeus, *Gypsonoma minutana* Hübner, *Pandemis cerasana* Hübner, *P. chondrillana* Herrich-Schäffer, *Ptycholoma lecheana* Linnaeus, *Tortrix viridana* Linnaeus, *Spilonota ocellana* Fabricius (Tortricidae).

Dolichogenidea laevis (Ratzeburg, 1848)

Microgaster laevis Ratzeburg, 1848.

Apanteles laevis: Wilkinson, 1945: 171; Telenga, 1955: 71; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 418; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 211.

Apanteles tersus Papp, 1973.

Distribution. Ukraine: West. — Europe: Western Europe (Germany, Great Britain, France), Eastern Europe (Czech Republic, Hungary, Romania, Slovakia).

Hosts. Parasites of *Recurvaria nanella* Denis & Schiffermüller (Gelechiidae), *Acrocercops brongniardella* Fabricius (Gracillariidae), *Adoxophyes orana* Fischer von Röslerstamm, *Clavigesta sylvestrana* Curtis (Tortricidae).

Dolichogenidea lineipes (Wesmael, 1837)*

Microgaster lineipes Wesmael, 1837.

Apanteles lineipes: Nixon, 1972: 724; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 443; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 189; Zerova, Kotenko *et al.*, 1989: 153.

Material. Western Ukraine, no geographical data, no date, 1♂, 2♀; Kyiv Region, no collecting date, 3♂, 5♀ (A. Kotenko) (SIK).

Distribution. Ukraine: West, Center. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Latvia, Lithuania), Southern Europe (Croatia, Italy), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Israel, Mongolia.

Hosts. Lepidopteran from the families Gracillariidae, Tortricidae, Yponomeutidae, including *Caloptilia semifascia* Haworth (Gracillariidae), *Clavigesta sylvestrana* Curtis, *Acleris (Croesia) bergmanniana* Linnaeus, *Epinotia abbreviana* Fabricius, *E. immundana* Fischer von Röslerstamm, *E. pusillana* Peyerimhoff, *E. pygmaeana* Hübner, *E. sordidana* Hübner, *Rhyacionia buoliana* Denis & Schiffermüller, *Rh. pinivorana* Lienig & Zeller, *Tortrix viridana* Linnaeus, *Zeiraphera griseana* Hübner, *Z. rufimitrana* Herrich-Schäffer (Tortricidae), *Argyresthia goedartella* Linnaeus (Yponomeutidae).

Dolichogenidea longipalpis (Reinhard, 1880)

Apanteles longipalpis Reinhard, 1880; Telenga, 1955: 76; Nixon, 1965: 181; Tobias, 1971: 250, 1976: 201; Papp, 1981a: 265, 1983: 125; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 447; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 220.

Dolichogenidea longipalpis: Shaw, 2012: 178.

Apanteles tadzhicus Telenga, 1949.

Distribution. Ukraine: South. — Europe: Western Europe (Great Britain, Germany), Northern Europe (Finland), Southern Europe (Italy, Macedonia, Serbia), Eastern Europe (Hungary, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Armenia, China, Iran, Tajikistan, Turkey.

Hosts. Parasites of *Epichnopterix plumella* Denis & Schiffermüller (Psychidae), *Thiodia citrana* Hübner (Tortricidae).

Dolichogenidea mimi (Papp, 1974)

Apanteles mimi Papp, 1974: 325; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 442.

Dolichogenidea mimi Kotenko, 2013: 140.

Distribution. Ukraine: South. — Europe: Eastern Europe (Hungary, Moldova).

Hosts. Unknown.

Dolichogenidea pallidalata (Tobias, 1964)

Apanteles pallidalatus Tobias, 1964: 228, 1976: 205; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 457.

Distribution. Ukraine: South. — Europe: Eastern Europe (Romania); Kazakhstan.

Hosts. Parasites of *Ananarsia eleagnella* Kuznetsov and *A. lineatella* Zeller (Gelechiidae).

Dolichogenidea phaloniae (Wilkinson, 1940)

Apanteles phaloniae Wilkinson, 1940: 23; Tobias, 1971: 252, 1976: 195; Nixon, 1972: 714; Abdinbekova, 1973: 75; Papp, 1981b: 149; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 441.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, South. — Europe: Western Europe (Germany, Great Britain, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Lithuania), Southern Europe (Italy), Eastern Europe (Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Krasnodar Territory); Azerbaijan, Georgia, Israel.

Hosts. Parasites of *Aethes smeathmanniana* Fabricius (Tortricidae).

Dolichogenidea princeps (Wilkinson, 1941)

Apanteles princeps Wilkinson, 1941: 28; Nixon, 1972: 712; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 437; Papp, 1972: 712, 1981b: 150; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 441.

Dolichogenidea princeps: Kotenko, 2013: 140; Papp, 2014: 154.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, South. — Europe: Western Europe (Great Britain, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Southern Europe (Italy, Serbia, Spain), Eastern Europe (Hungary, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Primorsky Territory); Azerbaijan, Korea, Mongolia, Turkey; Tunisia.

Hosts. Parasites of *Ecebalia obscenella* Herrich-Schäffer, *E. virgaureae* Stainton and *Postvinculia lutipennella* Zeller (Coleophoridae).

Dolichogenidea punctiger (Wesmael, 1837)

Microgaster punctiger Wesmael, 1837.

Apanteles punctiger: Telenga, 1955: 65; Tobias, 1971: 253; Papp, 1981b: 151; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 433.

Dolichogenidea punctiger: Shaw, 2012: 179; Kotenko, 2013: 140.

Apanteles itea Nixon, 1972.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Belgium, France, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Switzerland, the Netherlands),

Northern Europe (Denmark, Sweden), Southern Europe (Croatia, Italy), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Russia, Slovakia).

Hosts. Parasites of *Caloptilia semifascia* Haworth, *Phyllonorycter junoniella* Zeller, *P. messaniella* Zeller (Gracillariidae).

Dolichogenidea seriphia (Nixon, 1972)

Apanteles seriphus Nixon, 1972: 731; Papp, 1981b: 150; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 444

Dolichogenidea seriphia: Papp, 2014: 154.

Distribution. Ukraine: South. — Europe: Southern Europe (Greece, Italy, Montenegro, Serbia, Spain), Eastern Europe (Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Russia, Slovakia); Iran, Turkey; Tunisia.

Hosts. Parasites of *Metzneria ehikeella* Gozmány (Gelechiidae) and *Parectopa ononidis* Zeller (Gracillariidae).

Dolichogenidea sicaria (Marshall, 1885)

Apanteles sicarius Marshall, 1885; Ivanov, 1898: 65; Wilkinson, 1945: 177; Telenga, 1955: 87; Tobias, 1971: 255, 1976: 199; Nixon, 1972: 722; Abdinbekova, 1975: 265; Papp, 1981b: 150; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 444; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 247; Zerova, Melika *et al.*, 1989: 42; Kotenko, 1997: 683.

Dolichogenidea sicaria: Papp, 1999: 560, 2014: 154.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, Center, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, France, Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Estonia, Finland), Southern Europe (Greece, Macedonia, Serbia, Spain), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Russia); Asian Russia (Omsk Region, Zabaikalskiy Territory, Amur Region, Khabarovsk Territory, Primorsky Territory, Kamchatka Territory); Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Turkey; Morocco, Tunisia; North America; New Zealand (introduced).

Hosts. Lepidopterans from the families Depressariidae, Gelechiidae, Gracillariidae, Momphidae, Plutellidae, Pyralidae, Tortricidae, including *Agonopterix arenella* Denis & Schiffmüller (Depressariidae), *Isophrictis anthemidella* Wocke, *Pexicopia malvella* Hübner (Gelechiidae), *Mompha sturnipennella* Treitschke (Momphidae), *Plutella xylotella* Linnaeus, *Pseudoplutella porrectella* Linnaeus (Plutellidae), *Etiella zinckenella* Treitschke (Pyralidae), *Aethes francillana* Fabricius, *Ancylis laetana* Fabricius, *Cochylimorpha straminea* Haworth, *Cochylis posterana* Zeller, *Epinotia pygmaeana* Hübner, *Eucosma aemulana* Schläger, *Lobesia botrana* Denis & Schiffmüller, *Sparganothis pilleriana* Denis & Schiffmüller (Tortricidae).

Dolichogenidea sophiae (Papp, 1972)

Apanteles sophiae Papp, 1981b: 150, 1999: 560; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 442; Kotenko, 1997: 683.

Distribution. Ukraine: West (Carpathian Mountains), Center, Crimea. — Europe: Eastern Europe (Hungary, Moldova, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Zabaikalskiy Territory); Armenia, Georgia, Turkey.

Hosts. Unknown.

Dolichogenidea turionellae (Nixon, 1971)

Apanteles turionellae Nixon, 1971: 361; Nixon, 1972: 714; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 437.

Distribution. Ukraine: West (Carpathian Mountains). — Europe: Western Europe (Austria).

Hosts. Parasites of *Coccyx mughiana* Zeller, *C. posticana* Zetterstedt, *C. turionella* Linnaeus (Tortricidae).

Dolichogenidea ultima (Kotenko, 1986)

Apanteles ultimus Kotenko in: Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 457.

Distribution. Ukraine: South, Crimea. — Europe: Eastern Europe (Russia).

Hosts. Unknown.

Dolichogenidea ultor (Reinhard, 1880)

Apanteles ultor Reinhard, 1880; Telenga, 1955: 55; Nixon, 1965: 126; Tobias, 1971: 256; Nixon, 1976: 695; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 456; Lăcătușu & Filipescu, 1989: 222.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, Center, East, South. — Europe: Western Europe (Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Southern Europe (Italy, Serbia, Slovenia), Eastern Europe (Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Azerbaijan, Georgia.

Hosts. Parasites of *Malacosoma neustrium* Linnaeus (Lasiocampidae), *Euproctis chrysorrhoea* Linnaeus, *Eu. similis* Fuessly, *Leucoma salicis* Linnaeus, *Orgyia antiqua* Linnaeus (Lymantriidae).

Dolichogenidea victoriata (Kotenko, 1986)

Apanteles victoriatus Kotenko in: Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 441.

Distribution. Ukraine: South. — Europe: Eastern Europe (Russia).

Hosts. Unknown.

Genus *Illidops* Mason, 1981

Type species: *Apanteles butalidis* Marshall, 1887. Widely distributed small genus of c. 50 species in the World, about 30 in the Palearctic Region, and 10 in Ukraine. One species (*I. electilis*) has been recorded by the author for the first time for Ukraine. Species of this genus parasitize in lepidopteran caterpillars from the families Psychidae, Pyralidae, Roeslerstammiidae, Scythrididae and Tortricidae.

Illidops butalidis (Marshall, 1889)

Apanteles butalidis Marshall, 1889; Fahringer, 1935: 157; Telenga, 1955: 83; Nixon, 1965: 183, 1976: 709; Papp, 1981a: 275, 1983: 126; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 424; Kotenko, 1997: 682.

Illidops butalidis: Papp, 1999: 560, 2014: 155.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Germany, Great Britain), Northern Europe (Sweden), Southern Europe (Croatia, Serbia, Spain), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Primorsky Territory, Zabaikalskiy Territory); Mongolia, Turkey; North Africa.

Hosts. Parasites of *Roeslerstammia erxlebella* Fabricius (Roeslerstammiidae), *Scythris picaepennis* Haworth (Scythrididae).

Illidops buteonis (Kotenko, 1986)

Apanteles buteonis Kotenko in: Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 424.

Distribution. Ukraine: South. — Europe: Eastern Europe (Russia).

Hosts. Unknown.

Illidops electilis (Tobias, 1964)*

Apanteles electilis Tobias, 1964: 226; Papp, 1981a: 273, 1983: 127; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 423.

Illidops electilis: Papp, 2014: 155.

Material. Ukraine: Donetsk Region, Zakotnoye, 21.07.1984, 2 ♀ (A. Kotenko); Kherson Region, Tchuruk Island, steppe, 7.06.2003, 3 ♀ (A. Kotenko) (SIZK).

Distribution. Ukraine: South. — Europe: Southern Europe (Croatia, Serbia), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Russia); Kazakhstan; Tunisia.

Hosts. Unknown.

Illidops kostylevi (Kotenko, 1986)

Apanteles kostylevi Kotenko in: Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 424.

Distribution. Ukraine: South. — Europe: Eastern Europe (Moldova, Russia).

Hosts. Unknown.

Illidops mutabilis (Telenga, 1955)

Apanteles mutabilis Telenga, 1955: 97; Tobias, 1971: 251; Papp, 1981a: 273, 1983: 127; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 422;

Illidops mutabilis: Papp, 1988: 150, 2014: 155; Kotenko, 2013: 140.

Apanteles szabo Papp, 1972.

Distribution. Ukraine: South. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, France, Germany), Southern Europe (Croatia, Serbia, Spain), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Georgia, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Turkey; Tunisia.

Hosts. Parasite of *Etiella zinckenella* Treitschke (Pyralidae).

Illidops naso (Marshall, 1885)

Apanteles naso Marshall, 1885; Papp, 1981a: 275, 1983: 127.

Apanteles contortus Tobias, 1964: 224; Abdinbekova, 1975: 260; Nixon, 1976: 712; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 425.

Apanteles crantor Nixon, 1965: 183.

Apanteles evander Nixon, 1965: 183.

Apanteles coresia Nixon, 1973.

Illidops naso: Papp, 1988: 150, 1999: 560; Shaw, 2012: 179.

Distribution. Ukraine: South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Great Britain, Switzerland), Northern Europe (Finland), Southern Europe (Croatia, Greece (incl. Crete), Macedonia, Serbia), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Moldova, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Afghanistan, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Kazakhstan, Korea, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan.

Hosts. Unknown.

Illidops rostratus (Tobias, 1976)

Apanteles rostratus Tobias, 1976: 248; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 422.

Illidops rostratus: Papp, 1988: 150.

Distribution. Ukraine: South, Crimea. — Europe: Eastern Europe (Russia); Armenia, Uzbekistan.

Hosts. Unknown.

Illidops sophrosine (Nixon, 1976)

Apanteles sophrosine Nixon, 1976: 709, 713; Papp, 1983: 128; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 424.

Illidops sophrosine: Papp, 1999: 560.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, East, South. — Europe: Southern Europe (Italy), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Russia); Asian Russia (Primorsky Territory, Zabaikalskiy Territory).

Hosts. Unknown.

Illidops suevus (Reinhard, 1880)

Apanteles suevus Reinhard, 1880; Papp, 1981a: 272, 1984a: 287, 1984b: 165; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 422; Kotenko, 1997: 683; Kotenko, 2013: 140.

Illidops suevus Papp, 1988: 150; 1999: 560.

Apanteles dion Nixon, 1965: 183.

Apanteles minutus Szépligeti, 1896.

Apanteles sesostris Nixon, 1976: 713.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, South. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, France, Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Southern Europe (Croatia, Greece, Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Irkutsk Region); Armenia, Iran, Kazakhstan, Korea, Mongolia.

Hosts. Parasite of *Epichnopteryx* sp. (Psychidae).

Illidops urgo (Nixon, 1965)

Apanteles urgo Nixon, 1965: 182, 1976: 710; Tobias, 1971: 256; Abdinbekova, 1975: 259; Papp, 1981a: 272, 1983: 128; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 423.

Illidops urgo: Kotenko, 2013: 140.

Distribution. Ukraine: South, Crimea. — Europe: Southern Europe (Croatia, Greece), Eastern Europe

(Hungary, Russia, Slovakia); Armenia, Azerbaijan, Mongolia, Turkey.

Hosts. Unknown.

Genus *Pholetesor* Mason, 1981

Type species: *Apanteles ornigis* Weed, 1887.

Widely distributed small genus, with about 40 species in the World, of them c. 20 species in the Palearctic Region, 12 in Ukraine, of which 3 species (*P. exiguus*, *P. laetus*, *P. maritimus*) were recorded for the first time for Ukraine by the author. Species of this genus parasitize in Lepidoptera caterpillars of seven families (most often Gracillariidae, Elachistidae, Coleophoridae).

Pholetesor arisba (Nixon, 1973)

Apanteles arisba Nixon, 1973: 209, 210; Papp, 1983: 131; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 413; Zerova *et al.*, 1992: 61.

Pholetesor arisba: Papp, 1999: 562, 2012: 185.

Distribution. Ukraine: South. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Germany, Great Britain, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Denmark, Norway), Southern Europe (Greece, Italy, Spain, former Yugoslavia), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Russia, Slovakia); China, Egypt, Israel; New Zealand.

Hosts. Parasite of *Stephensia brunnichella* Linnaeus (Elachistidae), *Phyllonorycter blancardella* Fabricius, *P. comparella* Dup. (Gracillariidae).

Pholetesor bicolor (Nees, 1834)

Microgaster bicolor Nees, 1834.

Apanteles bicolor: Ivanov, 1898: 66; Fahringer, 1935: 228; Telenga, 1955: 51; Nixon, 1973: 207, 211; Tobias, 1971: 243, 1976: 189; Papp, 1983: 131; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 411; Zerova *et al.*, 1992: 60, 91, 179.

Pholetesor bicolor: Shaw, 2012: 180; Papp, 1988: 148, 2012: 185, 2014: 155.

Microgaster ardeaepennellae Bouché, 1834.

Apanteles pedias Nixon, 1973; Kotenko, 2013: 140.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, North, Center, East, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Belgium, France, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Lithuania), Southern Europe (Croatia, Greece, Italy, Serbia, Spain (incl. Canary Islands)), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Kamchatka Territory); China, Georgia, Iran, Israel, Japan, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Turkmenistan; Tunisia; New Zealand.

Hosts. Parasites of *Aspilapteryx tringipennella* Zeller, *Caloptilia semifascia* Haworth, *Gracillaria syringella* Fabricius, *Phyllonorycter blancardella* Fabricius, *P. cavella* Zeller, *P. cerasicolella* H.-Sch., *P. comparella* Dup., *P. connexella* Zeller, *P. corylifoliella* Hübner, *P. emberizaepennella* Bouché, *P. junoniella* Zeller, *P. klemannella* Fabricius, *P. lantanella* Schr., *P. oxyacanthae* Frey, *P. populifoliella* Treitschke, *P. sorbi* Frey (Gracillariidae).

Pholetesor circumscriptus (Nees, 1834)

Microgaster circumscriptus Nees, 1834.

Apanteles circumscriptus: Wilkinson, 1938: 41–50; Nixon, 1965: 145; Nixon, 1973: 209, 211; Tobias, 1971: 244, 1976: 189; Papp, 1983: 131, 1999: 562; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 413; Zerova *et al.*, 1992: 60, 91, 179.

Pholetesor circumscriptus: Shaw, 2012: 180; Kotenko, 2013: 140.

Microgaster blancardellae Bouché, 1834.

Microgaster flavolimbatus Ratzeburg, 1848.

Microgaster lividipes Wesmael, 1837.

Microgaster umbellatarum Haliday, 1834.

Apanteles lautellus Marshall, 1885.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, North, Center, East, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Denmark, Finland, Latvia, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Croatia, Greece, Italy, Macedonia, Serbia, Spain), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Irkutsk Region, Khabarovsk Territory); Armenia, Azerbaijan, China, Georgia, Iran, Israel, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea; New Zealand. This species is also indicated for the Nearctic Region (Whitfield, 1997).

Hosts. Lepidopterans from the families Choreutidae, Coleophoridae, Elachistidae, Gracillariidae, including *Choreutis pariana* Clerck (Choreutidae), *Cepurga hemerobiella* Scopoli, *Phylloscheme glitzella* Hofmann (Coleophoridae), *Elachista gangabella* Zeller, *E. gleichenella* Fabricius, *E. humilis* Zeller, *E. luticomella* Zeller (Elachistidae), *Callisto denticulella* Thunberg, *Parornix avellanella* Stainton, *Phyllonorycter blancardella* Fabricius, *P. cavella* Zeller, *P. cerasicolella* Herrich-Schäffer, *P. corylifoliella* Hübner, *P. (Juxtafera) emberizaepennella* Bouché, *P. junoniella* Zeller, *P. lantanella* Schrank, *P. lautella* Zeller, *P. messaniella* Zeller, *P. nigrescentella* Logan, *P. oxyacanthae* Frey, *P. platani* Stainton, *P. populifoliella* Treitschke, *P. quercifoliella* Zeller, *P. rajella* Linnaeus, *P. scabiosella* Douglas, *P. sorbi* Frey, *P. spinicolella* Zeller (Gracillariidae).

Pholetesor elpis (Nixon, 1973)

Apanteles elpis Nixon, 1973: 209, 210; Tobias, 1976: 246; Papp, 1983: 132; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 413; Zerova *et al.*, 1992: 63.

Apanteles girkanus Tobias, 1976.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland), Southern Europe (Croatia, Greece), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Magadan Region, Primorsky Territory, Sakhalin Is.); Azerbaijan, Korea, Mongolia.

Hosts. Parasites of *Haploptilia serratella* Linnaeus (Coleophoridae), *Elachista cingillella* Herrich-Schäffer, *E. subnigrella* Douglas (Elachistidae), *Euspilapteryx auroguttella* Stephens, *Phyllonorycter blancardella* Fabricius, *P. comparella* Duponchel (Gracillariidae).

Pholetesor exiguus* (Haliday, 1834)

Microgaster exiguus Haliday, 1834.

Apanteles exiguus: Telenga, 1955: 51; Nixon, 1973: 208, 212; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 413

Pholetesor exiguus: Papp, 2014: 155.

Material. Ukraine: Kyiv Region, collecting date unknown, 2♂, 4♀ (Kotenko) (SIZK).

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, East. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Great Britain, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Norway), Southern Europe (Italy), Eastern Europe (Hungary, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Zabaikalskiy Territory, Sakhalin Is.); Iran, Korea, Mongolia; Tunisia.

Hosts. Parasites of *Phyllonorycter junoniella* Zeller (Gracillariidae).

Pholetesor laetus* (Marshall, 1885)

Apanteles laetus Marshall, 1885; Telenga, 1955: 51; Nixon, 1973: 208, 209; Papp, 1983: 133; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 411.

Pholetesor laetus: Papp, 1988: 149; Shaw, 2012: 181.

Apanteles metallicus Jakimavičius, 1972.

Material. Ukraine: Kyiv Region, 4.07.1984, 3♂, 2♀ (S. Sviridov) (SIZK).

Distribution. Ukraine: Center. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Denmark, Lithuania), Southern Europe (Serbia, Slovenia), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Russia); Asian Russia (Irkutsk Region, Zabaikalskiy Territory, Primorsky Territory, Sakhalin Is.); China, Japan.

Hosts. Parasites of *Biselachista scirpi* Stainton (Elachistidae), *Caloptilia elongella* Linnaeus, *C. semifascia* Haworth, *Phyllonorycter platani* Stainton, *P. rajella* Linnaeus, *P. stettinensis* Nicelli (Gracillariidae).

Pholetesor maritimus* (Wilkinson, 1941)

Apanteles maritimus Wilkinson, 1941; Nixon, 1973: 208, 214; Papp, 1983: 133; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 411.

Material. Odesa Region, Vilkovo, Kubanu Island, 9.10.1996, 1♂, 2♀ (A. Kotenko) (SIZK).

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, East. — Europe: Western Europe (France, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Denmark), Eastern Europe (Hungary, Poland, Russia, Slovakia); China, Kyrgyzstan.

Hosts. Parasites of *Bucculatrix maritima* Stainton (Bucculatricidae).

***Pholetesor moldavicus* (Tobias, 1975)**

Apanteles moldavicus Tobias in: Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 371.

Pholetesor moldavicus: Shaw, 2012: 182.

Distribution. Ukraine: South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (France, Great Britain), Eastern Europe (Moldova, Russia, Slovakia); Armenia, Korea.

Hosts. Parasites of *Bucculatrix ulmella* Zeller, *B. thoracella* Thunberg (Bucculatricidae).

***Pholetesor nanus* (Reinhard, 1880)**

Apanteles nanus Reinhard, 1880; Ivanov, 1898: 61; Fahringer, 1935: 194; Telenga, 1955: 101; Nixon, 1973: 208, 215; Papp, 1983: 133; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 411.

Pholetesor nanus: Papp, 1988: 149; Shaw, 2012: 182.

Apanteles szoecsi Papp, 1973.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, North, Center, East. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, France, Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Italy, former Yugoslavia), Eastern Europe (Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); North America.

Hosts. Lepidopterans from the families Coleophoridae, Gracillariidae, Nepticulidae, including *Ascleriducta lithargyrinella* Zeller (Coleophoridae), *Phyllonorycter connexella* Zeller, *P. (Asymmetrivalva) dubitella* Herrich-Schäffer, *P. heegeriella* Zeller, *P. (Asymmetrivalva) hilarella* Zeller, *P. klemannella* Fabricius, *P. muelleriella* Zeller, *P. rajella* Linnaeus, *P. robiniella* Clemens, *P. (Asymmetrivalva) salicicolella* Sircom, *P. (Asymmetrivalva) salictella* Zeller, *P. strigulatella* Lienig & Zeller, *P. ulmifoliella* Hübner (Gracillariidae), *Stigmella tiliae* Frey (Nepticulidae).

***Pholetesor phaetusa* (Nixon, 1973)**

Apanteles phaetusa Nixon, 1973: 209, 213; Papp, 1983: 134; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 413.

Pholetesor phaetusa: Shaw, 2012: 182; Kotenko & Sviridov, 2012: 380.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, East, South. — Europe: Western Europe (Germany, Great Britain, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Finland, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Italy, former Yugoslavia), Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania, Russia); Asian Russia (Sakhalin Is.); Korea, Mongolia.

Hosts. Parasites of *Millieria dolosalis* Heydenreich (Choreutidae), *Biselachista trapeziella* Stainton, *Elachista albifrontella* Hübner, *E. apicipunctella* Stainton, *E. gangabella* Zeller, *E. humilis* Zeller, *E. poae* Stainton, *E. regificella* Sircom (Elachistidae), *Callisto denticulella* Thunberg, *Phyllonorycter junoniella* Zeller (Gracillariidae).

***Pholetesor tobiasi* (Balevski, 1980)**

Apanteles tobiasi Balevski, 1980; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 406; Kotenko, 1999: 547.

Distribution. Ukraine: Center, South. — Europe: Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Russia).

Hosts. Unknown.

***Pholetesor viminetorum* (Wesmael, 1837)**

Microgaster viminetorum Wesmael, 1837.

Apanteles viminetorum: Fahringer, 1935: 209; Tobias, 1971: 257; Nixon, 1973: 208, 213; Tobias, 1976: 189; Papp, 1983: 134; Tobias & Kotenko, 1986: 411.

Pholetesor viminetorum: Papp, 1988: 149; Shaw, 2012: 183.

Microgaster fuliginosus Wesmael, 1837.

Distribution. Ukraine: West, North, Center, East, South, Crimea. — Europe: Western Europe (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Great Britain, Switzerland, the Netherlands), Northern Europe (Denmark, Estonia, Lithuania, Sweden), Southern Europe (Italy, former Yugoslavia), Eastern Europe (Belarus, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia); Asian Russia (Primorsky Territory, Kamchatka Territory, Sakhalin Is., Kuril Is.); Azerbaijan, China, Georgia, Iran, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan; North America.

Hosts. Lepidopterans of the families Coleophoridae, Elachistidae, Gracillariidae, including *Casignetella galbulipennella* Zeller, *Haploptilia serratella* Linnaeus (Coleophoridae), *Biselachista trapeziella* Stainton, *Cosmiotes freyerella* Hübner, *C. stabilella* Stainton, *Elachista adscitella* Stainton, *E. albifrontella* Hübner, *E. apicipunctella* Stainton, *E. bedellella* Sircom, *E. bifasciella* Treitschke, *E. gleichenella* Fabricius, *E. humilis* Zeller, *E. maculicerusella* Bruand, *E. obliquella* Stainton, *E. regificella* Sircom, *E. triatomea* Haworth (Elachistidae), *Gracillaria syringella* Fabricius, *Leucospilapteryx omissella* Stainton (Gracillariidae).

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